

Annotatsiya

Sevinchxojaxon xonadoni tarixini yoritishda tarixiy yozma manbalar katta ahamiyatga ega. Ulardan samarali foydalanish ushbu davr tarixini chuqur o'rganish, bo'lib o'tgan siyosiy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy voqealarning to'la tasvirini qayta tiklash, ularning kelib chiqish sabablari va oqibatlarini to'g'ri tahlil qilish, davrning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy hamda madaniy hayotini to'laroq yoritishga yordam beradi. Maqolada Sevinchxojaxon xonadonining valiahd shahzodasi qaysi shaharni boshqarganligiga oydinlik kiritilgan.

Abstract

Historical written sources are of great importance in elucidating the history of the Sevinchhojakhan family. Effective use of them is a deep study of the history of this period, reconstruction of the full picture of political, socio-economic events, correct analysis of the causes and consequences of their origin, socio-economic and cultural aspects of the period. helps to brighten up your life. The article explains which city was ruled by the crown prince of the Sevinchhojakhan family.

Аннотация

Большое значение в освещении истории рода Севинчходжахан имеют исторические письменные источники. Эффективное их использование заключается в глубоком изучении истории этого периода, воссоздании полной картины политических, социально-экономических событий, правильном анализе причин и последствий их возникновения, социально-экономических и культурных аспектов периода. помогает сделать вашу жизнь ярче. В статье объясняется, каким городом правил наследный принц из рода Севинчходжахана.

Kalit so'zlar va iboralar: Sevinchxojaxon, tarixiy manbalar, ilmiy adabiyor, tadqiqot, valiahd, "Tarixiy Rashidiy", "Boburnoma", "Shayboniynoma", Ahsi, Toshkent, Shohruhiya

Key words and expressions: Sevinchhojakhan, historical sources, scientific literature, research, crown prince, "Tarikhi Rashidi", "Boburnoma", "Shaibaninoma", Akhsi, Tashkent, Shahrukhiya.

Ключевые слова и выражения: Севинчходжахан, исторические источники, научная литература, исследования, наследный принц, «Тарихи Рашиди», «Бобурнома», «Шайбанинома», Ахси, Ташкент, Шахрухия.

The Shaibani dynasty, which came to power in Movarounnahr in the 16th century, ruled their country in the form of a udel. In the process of dividing the territories occupied by Muhammad Shaibani Khan to his close relatives, in 1503, after the campaigns against the Kazakhs in 1509, he gave the properties of Fergana to Sevinchhoja Khan in the form of suurghol. After Shaibani Khan's death, Sevinchhoja Khan took the territories belonging to him from Ahmed Qasim Kohbara, one of the amirs of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur Mirza, and the

Fergana Valley from the Mongol khan Sultan Said Khan. Sevinchhojaghan managed his properties in Tashkent and Ferghana Valley until 1525.

We relied on historical sources and scientific literature to study the subject under investigation. We approached the historical sources critically based on the degree of relevance of the authors to the events being narrated and their personal views. The method of comparative analysis was used in the process of logically connecting the information in the sources. Based on the development of historical events and phenomena in interregional relations, scientific hypotheses were expressed.

The author of the information about the history of Sevinchhojaghan's family is unknown "Tawarikh-i Guzida, Nusratnama", "Baburnoma" of Zahiriddin Muhammad Baburni, "Shaybaniinoma" of Kamaluddin Binai, "Shybbaniinoma" of Muhammad Saleh, Fazlullah ibn Rozbekhan al-Isfahani. "Mehmonnomayi Bukhara", "Habib us-siyar fi akhbori afrodi bashar" by Ghiyazidin Khondamir, "Tarihi Alamoroi Abbasi" by Iskandarbek Munshi, "Tarihi Rashidi" by Mirza Muhammad Haydar, "Musaxhir al-bilad" by Muhammadyar ibn Arab Qataghan, Hafiz Tanish al-Bukhari's "Abdullanama" is partially described in historical sources such as "Tarikh" by Shah Mahmud ibn Mirza Fazil Churas, "Tarikh Qasira" by Mulla Sharafuddin A'lam¹.

The analysis of historical sources and scientific literature shows that in 1525, the news of Sevinchhoja Khan's death caused political instability in the Ferghana Valley. Haidar Mirza says the following about this: "When they heard that Sevinchhoja Khan was dead, all the inhabitants of those lands - scientists, artisans, farmers - all stood up. They thought that after Sevinchhojaghan's death, there would still be no unity among the Uzbeks, and they said: "We will occupy Andijan and strengthen the fortress until the Uzbeks come to a clear stop, and we will climb the mountain ourselves. They made a plan saying that if the Uzbeks can't find us in the mountains, they won't be able to besiege the fort either². From this information in the source, it can be seen that the power of the Shaibanis in the Ferghana Valley was not strong among the intellectuals, artisans and farmers, who were the settled part of the population. This shows that in the first twenty years of their rule, the Shaibanis could not protect the interests of these sections of the population. The information about the fact that some governors appointed by the Shaybanites are not high among the people or among the influential priests is also found in the Manoqib. For example, it is written in "Mavlona Lutfullah Manoqibi" written by Muhammed Mufti Ohangarani, that the Mayor of Margilan often had conflicts with the residents of the city. "Mawlana Lutfullah said: - Muhammed Mufti Ahangarani writes, "When Mawlana Shah Husayn was giving a sermon in the Eidgah and coming down from the minbar, a man came and told Mawlana Shah Husayn his wish. He is the son of a foreigner, and he was arrested by the mayor of Marginon for enmity. The mayor of the city was also in the congregation when the poor Maulana made a complaint to Shah Husain. Then Maulana Shah Husayn looked at the governor and said, "Isn't there anyone who can arrest this stranger's child with hatred?" The governor got up and made a request to Maulana Shah Husain with some of his acolytes, and he released the child and handed it over to him³. In another story of the same content, it is said that Maulana Shah, who was the head of the madrasa in the city, complained about the tyranny of the mayor. After the death of Maulana Shah Husayn, the mayor was called to Tashkent and hanged for his sins. A few such examples

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² Мирзо Муҳаммад Ҳайдар. Тарихи Рашидий. – Б. 525.

³ Муҳаммад Муфти Оҳангароний. Мавлоно Лутфуллоҳ маноқибӣ. – Б. 27.

are given in Manoqib. Judging from the fact that Maulana Shah Husayn lived in the second half of the 15th century and the first half of the 16th century, it becomes clear that these events correspond to the time of Sevinchhoja Khan. This information from the source also indicates that Sevinchhojakhan's deputies in the Ferghana Valley do not have enough influence among the local population.

In our opinion, in 1525 Ferghana uprising, mainly residents of the city and surrounding villages must have participated. The nomadic and semi-nomadic population living on the mountain slopes did not support this uprising. Also, we did not find any information about the insurgents establishing contact with Sultan Said Khan and coordinating their actions with him. The Shaybani sultans also made a correct assessment of the political events in the Ferghana Valley and involved all their forces in this matter in order not to lose the valley. According to Haydar Mirza's information that Shaibani's army that arrived in Ferghana consisted of an army of one hundred thousand people, it is clear that all the forces in Movarounnahr were mobilized for this campaign⁴.

The Shaibanis tried to suppress the Andijan uprising, at least to prevent them from uniting with each other, until the arrival of Sultan Said Khan.

The Shaibani army, which was recruited to suppress the uprising, succeeded in encircling Andijan on the seventh day of the battle. As a result, Sultan Said Khan had no chance to unite with the rebels and he had to return to Kashgar. It seems that as a result of the siege of Andijan, Sultan Saidkhan, who could not unite with the forces there against the Shaibanis, gave up hope of occupying the valley and decided to leave the city of Uzgan and the fortress of Modu, which he had conquered by battle. Yuri Bregel also showed on his map that during the campaign of Sultan Said Khan in 1525, his troops arrived near Andijan⁵.

Since Fergana was one of the most important provinces in the eastern regions of the Shaybani state, the Shaybani sultans did not want to lose it, and involved all their forces in this campaign. Babur Mirza, who established his own state in Afghanistan, probably started military operations to conquer India at this time, so he did not pay attention to the rebellion in the Ferghana Valley. In any case, the lack of information about this uprising in "Boburnoma" encourages us to come to such a conclusion. In addition, Sultan Said Khan's claim to Ferghana Valley and Badakhshan probably caused Mirza Babur not to be distracted from the issue of India.

As a result of the death of Ismail Safavi in 1524, the internal political situation in the Safavid state became tense, and the Shaibanis made it possible to attract all their military forces to the Ferghana Valley⁶.

As we said above, Sevinchhojakhan managed the Ferghana Valley through governors appointed by him. But the names of these governors are not preserved in the sources. Only in one of the labels of the "Collection of Labels" published by A. Juvonmardiev, the name of Muhammad Mamanbi is mentioned in the documents related to the period we are studying⁷. Although the label signed by Mamanbiy is not dated, it can be dated to the first quarter of the

⁴ Муҳаммад Ҳайдар Мирзо Тарихи Рашидий. – Б. 525.

⁵ Bregel Yuri. An historical atlas of central Asia. – Boston: Brill Leiden, 2003. – P. 53.

⁶ Eskandar Beg Monshi. History of Shah Abbas the Great / translated by Roger M. Savory – Colorado: Westview Press, 1930. – P. 73-74.

⁷ Жувонмардиев А. XVI – XIX асрларда Фарғонада ер-сув масалаларига доир. – Б. 78

16th century, based on the fact that this label was given to Fazil Ali, a landowner in the Karaskan region of Akhsi region. Because the chronological limit of the documents issued in the name of Fazil Ali is 1506-1532. Based on this label, it can be said that Akhsi province was ruled by a governor named Muhammad Mamanbiy. Unfortunately, there is no complete information about the period of his rule and the territories he ruled. However, from the information given in the work "Mavlano Lutfullah Manoqibi" by Muhammed Mufti Ohangarani, it appears that the governor of Margilan was directly subordinated to Sevinchhojakhan, who managed his estates from Tashkent⁸. Because according to the source, residents of the city of Margilan were dissatisfied with their governors and appealed to the Khan of Tashkent several times. Khan Toshkeni took measures against these governors. Based on this, it can be said that the governors of major cities in the Fergana Valley, including Akhsi, Andijan, Margilan and Khojand, were directly subordinated to Sevinchhojakhan.

After Sevinchhojakhan's death, power passed to his son Keldi Muhammad. Although Keldi Muhammad ruled the state from Tashkent, the Ferghana Valley was part of his state. As in the time of Sevinchhoja Khan, during the time of Keldi Mohammad, the Fergana valley was divided into several administrative units and managed by the governors of large cities such as Andijan, Akhsi, Margilan, and Khojand. Unfortunately, there is no information about their names in the sources.

Keldi Muhammad Sultan (also known as Sultan Muhammad Bahadir in historical sources) ruled the city of Shahruhiya during the reign of his father Sevinchhoja Khan⁹.

Historian Muhammadyar ibn Arab Qataghan Keldi wrote about Muhammad: "After his father's death, he became the owner of the state and the country, the owner of the crown and the throne in Tashkent region for a few days in the alliance of Uzbek emirs, and he ruled the kingdom and government in justice. A few days after this news, he also fell in love with his father. This event happened in 939 (1532 AD). His reign was eight years. Keldi Muhammad Sultan left a son named Hasan Khan. Hasan Sultan was under the tutelage of his uncle Baraq Khan for a short time and died of his own death. However, there are no descendants of him"¹⁰.

Юқорида таъкидлаганимиздек, 1525 йил 23 июль куни Севинчхожахон Тошкентда вафот этгандан сўнг Келди Муҳаммад султон отаси ўрнига тахтга чиқади. Укаси Наврўз Аҳмадхон эса Шохруҳия шаҳрига ҳоким қилиб тайинланади. Бундан кўринадики, Тошкент ва Фарғона мулкларининг валиаҳди Шохруҳия шаҳрига ҳокимлик қилиши ўзига ҳос анъанага айланган эди. Shohruhiya shahri Ohangaron daryosi bo'yida joylashgan bo'lib, juda qulay geopolitik o'ringa ega edi. Sababi bu hududdan Toshkentdan Farg'ona vodiysi va Movarounnahrning markaziy qismlariga olib boruvchi yo'llarni nazorat qilish imkonini berar edi. Shuning uchun Sevinchxojaxon xonadoni valiahdi ushbu shaharni hokimligiga tayinlangan¹¹.

According to historical sources, Khoja Jalaluddin Yusuf Kashgari was the prime minister of Keldi Muhammad Sultan's government.

Sultan Keldi Muhammad, like his father Sevinchhoja Khan, tried to establish good neighborly relations with the state of Saidia, which neighbors the Ferghana Valley to the east,

⁸ Муҳаммад Муфти Оҳангароний. Мавлоно Лутфуллоҳ маноқиби. – Б. 27.

⁹ Восифий. Бадоеъ ул-вақоеъ. – Б. 131.

¹⁰ Муҳаммадёр ибн Араб Қатаған. Мусаххир ал-билод. – Б. 167.

¹¹ Султонов Ў. Тошкент мулки Шайбонийлар даврида: Суюнчхожахон хонадони бошқаруви ҳақида айрим қайдлар // Sharqshunoslik. - Тошкент, 2014. – Б. 7-14.

and with the Kyrgyz tribes living in the northern regions. Some of the Kyrgyz tribes living on the northern borders of the valley were subordinate to the Saidiya state, while another part was dependent on the Kazakh khans. Keldi Muhammad Sultan tried to effectively use the rivalry between the Kazakh Khans and the Saidis to secure the Ferghana Valley. The favorable political situation that arose in the Kazakh Khanate after the death of Kasim Khan in 1521 made it possible to conduct such a policy. In particular, we can see this in the case of the Kazakh sultan Tahir Khan. According to historical sources, Tahir Khan was incompetent in the political and military spheres. After he was defeated in 1523-1524 in the fight with the Mangits, he fled to Mongolia with two hundred thousand inhabitants. Although Sultan Said Khan initially helped Tahir Khan, his attempts to sway the Kyrgyz to his side led to a deterioration in relations with the Mongol Khan¹².

This created favorable conditions for Keldi Muhammad Sultan. According to Mahmud bin Wali, "Tahir Khan, the son of Adik Khan, who started to rule the entire Kipchak steppe and some regions of Mongolia after Kasim Khan, because of his rough character, annoyed the hearts of the tribes and warriors." After he was abandoned by the chiefs and nobles of the country, he turned to Keldi Muhammad Sultan for help. Sevinchhojakhan's son and successor agreed to help him, and they exchanged ambassadors several times. The ambassadors were received with respect on both sides. When the news of the Kazakh khan's appeal to the Sultan for help, his promise of friendship and alliance with him reached the ears of his enemies, they were horrified." It is clear from this that Tahir Khan turned to Sultan Keldi Muhammad for help after his relationship with Sultan Said Khan worsened and he could not get along with his subordinates. At this time, the Kazakhs were under the influence of the Nogais in the northwest, and the Mongols in the southeast. It was not good for the Tashkent Khan that Sultan Said Khan became stronger. Sultan Keldi Muhammad, who was afraid of the strengthening of the Khan of Kashgar, who did not give up his claims to the Ferghana Valley, considered it necessary to support the Kazakhs. Abdurashid Khan, the son of the Mongol Khan Sultan Said Khan, and the Kazakh ambassadors who came to ask for help in the fight against the Nogais were well received in Tashkent. In 1525, Keldi Muhammad formed an alliance with Tahir Khan, the nephew and successor of the late Kazakh Khan Kasim Khan. After this alliance, the Kazakh nobles who abandoned Tahir Khan returned to him. In addition, the Mongolian army led by Abdurashidkhan, who heard about the alliance, stopped marching and retreated from Aksuv. The pressure of the Nogai on the Kazakhs also decreased. This indicates that Keldi Muhammad Sultan's position in this area was very strong.

In conclusion, the reason why the crown princes of the Sevinchhojakhan dynasty, who ruled the northeastern regions of the Shaibani state, were appointed as governors of the city of Shahruhiya was that the city of Shahruhiya was located on the banks of the Ahangaron River and had a very favorable geopolitical position. From this area, it was possible to control the roads leading from Tashkent to the Fergana Valley and the central parts of Movarounnahr.

¹² Мирзо Мухаммад Хайдар. Тарих-и Рашиди. – Б. 522, 526.

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